

Australian amphibian and reptile genomics Initiative Communications Policy v1.0

The Australian amphibian and reptile genomics Initiative has a strong interest in seeing that the data and capability produced by the Initiative is actively communicated to and used by the scientific and wider communities. All users of the data and capability produced through the initiative are expected to exhibit professional courtesy and utilise the data with the highest scientific integrity. When a substantial proportion of the data has been provided through the research activities of others, Bioplatforms strongly encourages investigators to discuss details and expectations of the project, as well as issues of authorship and acknowledgement on publications, prior to the start of the study.

1. General request for all Communications

All communications (scientific or general publications and presentations) that arise from the Australian amphibian and reptile genomics consortium's work will appropriately acknowledge the input of all relevant contributors. The publications should specify the collaborative nature of the project, and authorship is expected to include all those contributing significantly to the work (see sections below).

Add the following text to the acknowledgements for general consortium recognition:

"We would like to acknowledge the contribution of the Australian amphibian and reptile genomics¹ consortium in the generation of data used in this publication. The Australian amphibian and reptile genomics initiative is supported by funding from Bioplatforms Australia through the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS), the Australian National University, the University of Canberra, the Australian Museum, Museums Victoria and the South Australian Museum".

If relevant, also credit other organisations involved in collection of the particular data stream (as listed in 'credit' in the metadata record). The citation in a list of references is: Australian amphibian and reptile genomics consortium [year-of-data-download], [full metadata title], [data-access-URL], accessed [date-of-access].

2. Use of data by the Consortium

The Consortium reserves the right to conduct 'global analyses' across these genomics reference datasets and publish the results in the scientific literature, provided this is done in a timely fashion. The Consortium Data Policy² outlines the data sharing expectations and responsibilities.

3. Use of data by investigators within or outside of the Consortium

Users of Consortium data, whether members of the Consortium³ or not, should be aware of the publication status of the data they use and treat them accordingly. For example, all investigators including data from other Consortium members should discuss use with the sample producer(s) before using unpublished data in their individual publications (see guidelines below).

Investigators outside of the Consortium are free to use data generated by the initiative, but are asked to follow the guidelines developed at the Ft. Lauderdale meeting⁴. Specifically, data users should cite the source of the data and should acknowledge the sample producers and the funding partners (see section 1). In addition, the data users are asked to recognise the interests of the sample producers in publishing reports on the generation and analysis of their data, as described previously. Datasets from the Australian amphibian and reptile genomics Initiative may be released to public databases as pre-publication data and remain unpublished until they appear in peer-reviewed publications. Outside investigators who perform an in-depth analysis of data and are interested in publishing a report before the sample producers do so should discuss their results with the sample producer(s) and are encouraged to establish collaborations.

The following guideline may be used for acknowledgement and co-authorship, but specific details should be worked out

¹ www.ausargenomics.com

² www.ausargenomics.com/data-policy

³ A consortium member is someone who has contributed meaningfully to the science and/or management of the initiative, such as through active involvement in project development, working groups and panels, or contribution of samples.

⁴ <http://www.sanger.ac.uk/legal/assets/fortlauderdalereport.pdf>

between parties beforehand. Principal Investigators may wish to consider the proportion of data being used as a result of another Principal Investigators research activities.

As a guideline, in addition to the acknowledgement of the Australian amphibian and reptile genomics Initiative:

- Small and complementing dataset used: acknowledgement of the sample producer(s) optional
- Significant but disconnected data used (from many different sample producers): Consortium and sample producer(s) should be contacted for discussion, and receive acknowledgement
- Significant portion of data used – integral to the publication: co-authorship to be offered [sample producer(s) can naturally decline]

The Australian amphibian and reptile genomics Project Manager and/or Scientific Lead can also facilitate communication with sample producer(s).

4. Reporting of communications

Copies of communications are to be sent to the project manager (smazard@bioplatforms.com) for collection and circulated to the Consortium as appropriate.

For further information contact

Dr Sophie Mazard (smazard@bioplatforms.com) – Project Manager

Prof Craig Moritz (gekkojessie@gmail.com); Distinguished Prof Arthur Georges (georges@aerg.canberra.edu.au) – Scientific Leads